

THE USE OF VIRTUAL PLATFORMS AND TECHNIQUES AS EDUCATIONAL MATERIALS IN LANGUAGE SKILLS ACQUISITION

Corina PANCO

grad didactic I

ORCID: 0000-0002-0443-2543

IPLT „M. Viteazul”

As teachers have always to review enrich and reconstruct activities they need to apply for a variety of classic- traditional techniques and virtual platforms.

We will try to present the importance of e-learning platforms and selective techniques for each particular activity that many come on students help to be more disciplined, as well as informed creative and motivated. This article will try to present how the combination of new-modern and traditional-classic teaching resources make teachers as well as students be more open minded to get the best and most useful information to improve activity, and creativity, to develop the cognitive emotional, behavioral, pragmatic and affective skills.

In the century we live with all-the worldwide access to information and communication, it is very important to take advantage of all resources, both human and technical that all countries of the European Union have. Teachers would make decisions according to the resources they would be able to use; **virtual platforms** and **educational techniques**.

Teachers always have to review, enrich and reconstruct activities in their APDs so that students can take action. Thanks to the new technologies and a great variety of classic-traditional techniques there is a great work as in class as in online teaching.

The use of e-Learning platforms and techniques create a special atmosphere and a more interactive and diverse experience.

We may say that e-Learning platforms and correct selected techniques for each particular activity help students be more disciplined as well as informed, creative and opened to all is new and classic and not at last they are helped to rise up their self-confidence.

Virtual or *classic* team work individual work may connect students for new collaborations and even to take part in big competitions.

In this way the combination of new-modern and traditional-classic teaching resources makes teachers as well as students be more creative, open-minded to get a better connection between the teacher and the student, the virtual e-Learning platforms and traditional techniques.

To achieve these objectives, teachers need to be trained in **creativity**. This daily training is based on the development of **cognitive, emotional, behavioral, pragmatic and affective skills**. So, teachers need to be trained in a way they can transfer knowledge using new materials that complement the classic ones. Besides this, it is important to have an appropriate training in socio-emotional and motivational-development.

Teachers, therefore make a multi selection process; they select the most suitable activities, the best strategies and also the best approach for each class, according to Littlejohn (1998) teachers' action consists in **adopting, rejecting, adapting, complementing and turning** the use of selected resources into an object of a critical approach.

As an example, to develop and improve students' creativity there was use the e-Learning platform **Seesaw**. It is a platform used for students' engagement that inspires students of all ages to do their best and save teachers' time. In this case students use *creative tools* to take pictures, draw, record videos and more to capture learning in a portfolio. This platform shines as a digital tool too because it incorporates teacher-parent-student feedback.

To enable students to easily communicate with their classmates and instructors we may select the **Edmodo** platform; when communicating with colleagues Edmodo allows students to ask each other questions as well as view and respond to each other's; students can share and view information.

This educational technology platform for K-12 schools and teachers enables teachers to share content, distribute quizzes, assignments and manage communication with students, colleagues and parents.

Since the classroom environment changes the English language learners need a variety of language experiences. For example, to teach **vocabulary** students need to learn vocabulary in Context and with visual clues to help them understand.

Computers can incorporate various learning strategies as well as accommodate a variety of learning styles. As an example, it is the **Scratch** platform. In this free programming language and online community students can create their own interactive *Stories, games animation*.

In the Landerholm, Karr and Mushi project students created book reports with their parents on the computer's current software always for much *vocabulary comprehension and creativity* such as including *sounds, videos*, clipart and photos into the text of the report. Doing the "*book reports*", it encouraged the children to read more and more books.

We should guide our students to apply and use the numerous software packages for improving; *spelling, phonics skills, grammar* because all language experience are valuable to assist in *reading* ability.

There are also a variety of interactive choices students can use to read the story including: real voices, that read aloud, music and sound effects. The story is also highlighted, so readers can follow along with the text.

In a study conducted by the Liaw, computer books were used to investigate whether computers increase verbal interaction between students. These computers books are interactive stories that appear on the computer screen as an actual book with text and illustration.

This study was conducting by videotaping students' interactions while using the computers books Initially students had limited English language proficiency, there was a lot of computer related talk, but as the students became more familiar with the format of the stories and software, their talk became story related in subsequent sessions. Overall, the study concluded that the verbal interaction and the use of a variety of language functions by English language learners can be facilitated by the use of the computers because the environment proved an opportunity for verbal interaction.

To conclude: for the beginning there was:

a) An incomprehensible situation (without feedback) T- transmitter
R-receiver

b) then: A partial communicative comprehension

c) finally: A complete communication

TR

Teaching experience convinced many-teachers that disturbing incomprehensible and partial communication can be improved by the classical-traditional techniques too. As an example, it was taken “*the role of the text for developing the communicative ability*”. A text may be a new watched written or heard information that directs students on selecting information on a specific vocabulary, words for a good conversation, presentation or support a point of view. Text-also arouses students’ interest to find, to add and to debate on the new watched read or heard information. The formative function of a text, stimulates students to *think, analyze, associate, describe* and not at last *compare*. There was realized a set of 4 *techniques* which are usually used to improve, facilitate and evaluate students active and pragmatic understanding. 1) The **T-Graphic technique** is almost used when we have a debate, it causes a brainstorm which directs to new studied vocabulary and content 2) **Press-** it helps students to express their point of view and develops the capacity of argumentation.3) **Cube-** this technique has 6 key tasks used after a watched, listened or read material. It leads to describe, associate, analyze, apply, argue and compare. 4) **Reply, Throw and Ask-**it’s a technique based on stimulating and developing students’ ability to communicate through questions and answers on a given or studied topic.

In conclusion, it is worth painting out that incorporating technology and classical-traditional techniques into instruction can provide many important benefits to ESL students. *Available technologies and classical techniques* can greatly enhance both student-teacher and student-student interaction and can afford students increase opportunities for self-directed learning. However, to be most effective technology as well as techniques must be used to support well planned curricular goals and should involve carefully designed activities. So, computers and techniques are “tools” for increasing vocabulary, verbal interaction, the interest for studying and for much more students’ motivation in developing English Language Skills.

References

1. CASE, Carol, & TRUSCOTT, David, (1999) – *Reading and Writing Quarterly: Overcoming Learning Difficulties*, Boston.
2. HERLIN, W. R., ALBERECHT L. Y. (1990) *Study and Learning*. – Kendall: Hunt Publ. Co.
3. JOYCE, B., WELL, M. (1990) *Models of Teaching*. – New York: Prentice Hall Inc.
4. KANG, Sarah, & DENNIS, J. R, (1995) – *Computers in the Schools*, New York.
5. KASPER, Loretta, (1998), *Interdisciplinary English*, New York.
6. LANDERHOLM, Eric, & KARR, John, (2000) – *A Collaborative Approach to Family Literacy Evaluation Strategies*, New York.
7. Littlejohn, A. (1998) The analysis of language teaching material: inside the Trojan Horse. En B. Tomlinson (edit), *Materials development in language Teaching*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
8. LEWIS, Peter, (1997) – *Learning and Leading with Technology*, Washington, D. C.
9. TRENCHS, Marianne, (1996) – *Writing strategies in a second language*, New York.
10. MOSSTON, A. M., ASHWORTH, S. (1990) *The Spectrum of Teaching Styles*. – New York, London: Longman.